
Introversion-Extroversion and Vocational Interest Among Senior Secondary School Students in Jigawa state, Nigeria

By

Bashir Sabo

**Department of Psychology,
Jigawa State College of Education P. M. B 1002, Gumelkpi
Email: sabobashir5@gmail.com
Phone Number +2348022980008**

Abstract

This study investigated the influence of introversion–extroversion personality traits on vocational interests of senior secondary school students in Jigawa State, Nigeria. The objectives were to determine the prevalence of introversion–extroversion, identify vocational interests, and establish whether a relationship exists between the two variables. A total of 354 final-year students from eight senior secondary schools were selected using random sampling. Two standardized instrument the Introversion–Extroversion Scale (IES) and the Modified Vocational Interest Inventory (MVII) were used for data collection. Descriptive statistics and chi-square analysis were employed for data analysis. Results showed that extroverted students (66.9%) were more prevalent than introverted students (33.1%). Vocational interest in social services (25.7%) was most dominant, followed by persuasive (22.9%), while artistic (2.8%) was least dominant. Findings further revealed no significant relationship between personality traits and vocational interests. The study concludes that personality type may not strongly predict vocational interests among secondary school students in Jigawa State and recommends comprehensive career guidance and counseling interventions.

Keywords: Introversion, extroversion, vocational interest, personality traits, Jigawa State

Background to the Study

In any society, it appears no two persons are exactly the same no matter how close, even if they are identical twins. This arouses the interest of psychologists to investigate the differences and similarities that exists among people. Cole (2010) and others posit that an individual's personality determines what he really wants in life; and there is no fulfilment in life without engaging in a vocation that is in tandem with one's personality orientation. Personality is the total characteristics of an individual, including such that interest him/her and gives satisfaction.

Many Nigerians (people living in Jigawa State inclusive) have expressed their worries about lack of concern by both teachers and parents about the personality traits of the students most especially before choosing a particular vocation which normally ends in regrets. While some blamed the government for the entire mess, others are pointing accusing finger to the school managers. No matter how brilliant a student is, his intelligence will come to naught if he cannot identify his/her personality trait and subsequently their vocational interest.

Major features of introversion among students include been passive, calm and detached from everyday world. They are also good visionaries and day-dreamers and have difficulty coping with everyday life. On the other hand, features of extroversion may include: been adaptive easily, obey society rules, objective in all aspects of life, repress feelings and emotions, seek new experiences and focus mostly on pleasure and happiness.

Adetayo (2017) also admits that thousands of senior secondary school students are in the crowd of confused vocation seekers, either through the influence of peer groups, the environment, teachers, counsellors or even family influences. In essence, an inappropriate personality development is a clear pointer to disaster in future.

Oyeseni (2016) opines that vocational interest is developed from an individual's basic personality traits, likes and dislikes, weakness and strengths, values and skills. There is need to call the attention of educationists, teachers, parents and counsellors to seriously consider the personality type of a student or child when dealing with him/her, most especially in the area of vocation to practice. The destinies of many people are ruined for lack of proper information.

The theoretical framework of this investigation is being hinged on Holland's personality type and vocational interest theory. This is because the theory attempted to match people's personality type and their vocational interest. Holland opined that if an individual's personality type fits his vocational type, they enjoy and stay longer time fulfilled in the job and in life.

Holland identified six personality types that are important to consider in matching people's psychological make-up in vocational interest. These are: realistic, investigative, artistic, social, enterprising, and conventional

Bellamy (2017) carried out a study on vocational aspiration, expectation and beliefs of African American, white and Hispanic males with Holland social personality types. The study used twenty-two (22) African Americans, thirty-eight (38) white and eight (8) Hispanic males (in sub-urban high schools).

Below are the results: there were no differences in vocational aspiration and expectation either by race or by Holland's social personality types. The only difference observed in vocational belief by race was that African-Americans scored higher than white and Hispanic in their beliefs that approval of others was not important in choosing vocation. Differences in

vocational beliefs by Holland social personality type score higher than low social personality types on all four scales; showing as follows:

- i. A willingness of working harder despite facing uncertain futures
- ii. A greater inclination to persevere even in the face of failure
- iii. Envisioning greater capacity to pursue job satisfaction even if it means changing job in the process
- iv. Extroverts exhibit greater intelligence than introverts; this means ability to relate to other people. Moreover, extroverts are likely to enjoy and benefit from a noisy environment with regard to work performance, while quiet condition enhances the performance of introverts.

Nworah (2015) researched on the factors that influence vocational interest among senior secondary school students in Onitsha Zone, South Eastern Nigeria. The study had a population of 47,299 SS II students with sample of 400 students. Three hypotheses were formulated using the motivation occupational preference Scale (MOPS) as the questionnaire, the mean and the test statistical analysis, showed the following result: 76% of the boys preferred professional courses like law, medicine and geology, 98% girls preferred people oriented careers such as banking, broadcasting and teaching. That students choose vocations without considering the factor that influence vocation, such as interest, intellectual ability, personality of the person concerned, aptitude etc.

Nworah recommended that students should be made to understand that a realistic career choice is based on interest, ability and self-concept and not to be dictated by parents or Guardians.

Hirschi (2015), Conducted a research on "Vocational interests and Career goal Development in relations to personality in middle adolescence". This longitudinal study examined development of things/people and ideas, vocational interests and Career goals in relation to Big five personality traits among 292 Swiss adolescents with a cross lagged panel design with two measurement points over one year from seventh to eighth grade. Interests and goals were significantly related within time and showed significant attraction across time. Traits related significantly and equally to interests and goals within time and predict their development across time except for people goals. Goals and interest possessed incremental Validity above traits in affecting each other. Implications include the need to account for dynamic processes in the development of goals and interests and their systematic relations to traits in theory and practice.

Methodology

The research design for this study was descriptive survey. The descriptive survey design describes the characteristics of the population (i.e students) being studied. Descriptive survey research answers questions such as: who, what, where, when, and how of an observed problem (Sambo, 2017). Two sets of questionnaires were used as instruments for data collection. They are the introversion-extroversion scale (IES) and the modified vocational interest inventory (MVII).

The introversion-extroversion scale (IES) was developed by McCroskey in 1998. The eighteen items were drawn from the work of Eysenck. The alpha reliability estimates have been above 80. The IES was used without any modification as the items were clear and without any ambiguities. However, the second instrument titled MVII was adapted from the vocational interest inventory designed by the late professor Bakare (1977) to assess vocational interest of an individual or group of individuals. Alterations were made to this

instrument by reducing the number of items from 100 to 50; the scale was also changed to a 4point likert scale instead of the original 5points by removing the indifferent option.

Population of the study

The population of this study is composed of final year students (2022/2023 session) randomly selected from senior secondary schools across the three senatorial zones of Jigawa state. However, Arabic, science and technical schools were exempted because their students are offering restricted courses. A sample size of three hundred and fifty four (354) of both male and female students was used across eight senior secondary schools.

Table I: List of schools and final year students' population and sample sizes.

S/N	Name Of School	No. Of SSS III Students	Sample Size
1.	GDSS Lautai	880	82
2.	GGSS Danzomo	290	23
3.	GUSS Ringim	660	60
4.	GDSS Babura	322	26
5.	GUSS B/Kudu	590	53
6.	DMISS Dutse	475	40
7.	GDSS Birniwa	380	32
8.	GDSS Fantai	449	38

Source: Jigawa State Ministry of Education, 2022/2023 session.

Data Analysis

Data collected were analyzed using percentage and frequency count for the demographic data. Means statistics was used to answer research questions. The chi-square statistics was used to analyze hypothesis and it is given by the formula:

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(O_1 - e_1)^2}{e_1}$$

Where O_1 – represents observed frequencies

e_1 – represent the expected frequencies

Table 2: Distribution of final year students on introversion-extroversion in Jigawa state

Category	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Extroversion	237	66.90
Introversion	117	33.10
Total	354	100.00

Table 2 shows that two hundred and thirty seven (237) students (66.90%) were extroverted while one hundred and seventeen (117) were introverts. Majority of the students are therefore extroverts.

Table III: Vocational interest of final year senior secondary school students in Jigawa state.

Vocational interest	Frequency	Percentage(%)
outdoor	40	11.30
Mechanical	30	8.50
Computational	20	5.60
Scientific	20	5.60
Persuasive	81	22.90
Artistic	10	2.80
Literary	21	5.90
Musical	20	5.60
Social service	91	25.70
Clerical	21	5.90
Total	354	100

In the above table, ten (10) categories of vocational interests have been isolated. The frequency counts show that students' vocational interests is as follows: mechanical 30 (8.50%), computational 20 (5.60%), scientific 20 (5.60%), persuasive 81 (22.90%), artistic 10 (2.80%), literary 21 (5.90%), musical 20 (5.80%), social service 91 (25.70%), and clerical 21 (5.90%). From the analysis, vocational interest in the social services is the most dominant followed by persuasive while the least dominant is artistic.

This investigation revealed that majority of the final year senior secondary school students (2022/2023 session) in Jigawa state were extroverted.

Also from this investigation the researcher gathered that the vocational interest in the social services is the most dominant followed by persuasive while the least dominant is artistic.

It was also discovered that there is no significant relationship between introversion-extroversion personality traits and vocational interests of final year senior secondary school students the findings made in this investigation, the following recommendations have been made:

1. Ministry of Education in Jigawa State as well as in other states of the federation, should place more emphasis on other external factors like income or prestige in the process of career guidance in order to enable parents to allow their children to choose vocations based on their interests and abilities. Also students should be helped to understand that a realistic career choice could be made based on interest, ability, and job prestige, and not necessarily with reference to parental occupation or student personality.
2. Guidance and Counseling Service Units and the media outfits should put in more efforts in the provision of career information and adequate guidance, which will enable students to understand that vocational interests could be established without reference to personality traits because careers are not classified according to personality types.

Conclusion

This investigation started with the intention to examine the influence of introversion-extroversion personality type on vocational interest among senior secondary school students in Jigawa State. The personality traits (introversion-introversion) of the student do not in any way influence their vocational interests. This shows that students can take decisions on occupation of choice without giving due regards to their personality traits. The influence of

external factors such as income and prestige may have been reflected on the students' sense of reason. That there is no right or wrong occupational choice but interest must be matched with ability and other external dispositions where students can demonstrate corresponding ability and have the inner motivation to engage in a particular vocational activity. Success in the workplace might be more guaranteed when occupational choices are informed on the basis of external factors.

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